

4B_2 Metadata entry into an FDP

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Introduction

After implementing an FDP in [4B_1b FDP reference implementation](#) you now need to enter the data into the system. In this page we outline the steps for this.

Import the model into the FDP

Firstly, you need to provide the model you will be using to the FDP. You can import the model using [GitHub - Health-RI/FairDataPointSchemaTool](#).

 You can change the metadata schema version by switching the `-i` parameter to the appropriate properties file.

Alternatively, this can be done manually following this tutorial: [Importing shacl files in the FDP](#)

[- Front end](#)

Import the data into the FDP

After the correct model is available in the FDP you can provide your data. Ideally this can be an automated process using a script from the source of your metadata to the FDP. For this see [4 B_2a Automate export from your local system](#) an example using XNAT (image2catalog) and python [4B_2b Example python code to upload metadata to FDP](#) (SeMPyRO package)

Alternatively, the data can be entered **manually**. Here is the process for the manual metadata entry.

Manual data entry

⚠ Before entering data into your FDP validate your metadata model by contacting servicedesk@health-ri.nl. If you are directly using RDF format, you can additionally use [Health-RI RDF Validator](#)

1. Login to the FDP as an admin.
 - a. Alternatively, admin can create a data provider account for another user of the FDP and add them to a pre-existing Catalogue.
 - i. Navigate to the [users](#) and click on **+ Create user**
 - ii. Enter the name of the user and email.
 - iii. Click on **Create user**.
 - iv. Navigate to a pre-existing catalogue
 - v. Go to settings > users > invite user and search for the user
 - vi. Set the membership to **Data provider**
 - vii. Click on **invite**.
 - viii. This user is now allowed to create datasets and distributions in a catalogue.

Create a Catalogue

2. Navigate to Catalogs and click on +Create
3. Fill in the information about a catalogue as described in [GitHub - Health-RI/health-ri-metadata: health ri metadata schemas](#)
4. Click on **Save**. You will be taken to a new catalogue page
5. Publish the catalogue by clicking on **Publish**.

⚠ Saving process can take up to a minute
You need to fill all mandatory fields to be able to save the dataset

ℹ If not using a variable with mandatory subvariables the variable needs to be manually removed.

Create a Dataset

6. To create a dataset click on **+Create** button. A new page will open where you can enter your metadata.
7. After filling your metadata click on **Save** on the bottom of the page. You will then be redirected to the dataset page.

⚠ Saving process can take up to a minute

You need to fill all mandatory fields to be able to save the dataset

 If not using a variable with mandatory subvariables the variable needs to be manually removed.

8. To publish the dataset click on **“Publish”** on the top right of the page. A dialog will pop up requiring to confirm the action.

Create a distribution

9. To create a distribution of your dataset click on **+Create** in the top right corner. You can then fill out your metadata in the form.

10. After filling your metadata click on **Save** on the bottom of the page. You will then be redirected to the distribution page.

 Saving process can take up to a minute

You need to fill all mandatory fields to be able to save the distribution

 If not using a variable with mandatory subvariables the variable needs to be manually removed.

11. To publish the distribution click on **“Publish”** on the top right of the page. A dialog will pop up requiring to confirm the action.

12. You can repeat this process for multiple datasets and/or multiple distributions.

13. After entering your data, please check that the data is appears as expected in the FDP.

14. If data appear correctly, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl to begin **5. Metadata har**

vesting.

Editing existing data

1. Login into the FDP at <https://fdp-acc.healthdata.nl/>

2. In the search bar search for your **Catalog** or **Dataset** (or other metadata class you wish to edit)

3. Select you metadata.

4. To edit click **Edit**.

5. Edit and save.

Rights to edit metadata

Editing of metadata can be only done if you have the correct rights. Initially the person who created the metadata is the owner of the Catalog or Dataset and the only one who can edit them. To provide more individuals with editing rights:

1. Login into the FDP at <https://fdp-acc.healthdata.nl/>
2. In the search bar search for your **Catalog** or **Dataset** (or other metadata class you wish others to edit)
3. Click on **Settings**
4. In **Invite users** search for the user you wish to have access and editing rights. Select either Owner or Data provider. Owner can both edit and give rights to other users. Data providers can only edit.
5. Click **+Invite**

 The rights to edit are assigned directly per class, this means that rights to edit a Catalog do not provide editing rights for all Datasets in said catalog and need to be provided separately.

Common issues

∨ I lost my password

To reset your password, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl with the registered email

∨ I entered a field wrong, how can I change it.

On the catalog layer only admin can change the submitted metadata. If you need to change a field in Catalog, contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

For Datasets and Distributions you can find the edit option on the top right corner of the respective layer. If you have trouble finding your catalog, use the advanced search.

∨ Unable to update entity data.

One or more of the fields have been submitted in the wrong format. Please make sure to check variable's format in the model [GitHub - Health-RI/health-ri-metadata at master](https://github.com/Health-RI/health-ri-metadata)

Often, regards the **contact point email** which needs to be in vcard as <mailto:NAME@DOMAIN.nl> and cannot be submitted as NAME@DOMAIN.nl.

All **links** are required in IRI format, if your link includes characters not in ASCII it will also not be saved. Similarly links need to include the transfer protocol (ie. https://)

All time indicators (issued, modified) also need to follow the correct time format. Please check by selecting the a date on via the calendar rather than typing.

If you are unsure where the issue lies, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

∨ Unable to load (Dashboard/Catalog/Dataset)

If an update of the entity has been recently done, refreshing the page usually solves the issue.

If you are unsure where the issue lies, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

∨ Other issues

please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

✔ Next steps

If you have an FDP and compliant metadata ([4A Metadata mapping](#)) within your FDP, the data can be harvested by the National Catalogue. For this step see [5. Metadata harvesting](#) .

Add label